

SZ-SB-III-02-01 Search for other pupils (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091507
ID	SZ-SB-III-02-01
Title	Search for other pupils
Educational area	#school
Persona	P: Lisa - Pupil https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13682752
Short description	Lisa is looking for pupils (group) from the new school
Result	Networking via the BuddyFinder and mutual exchange on the topic
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• process "Contact with chemistry-loving 10th-graders"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lisa is registered at BIRD• Lisa is logged in to BIRD
Components	#buddyfinder #data-wallet #workspace #chat
Services / tools	

Problem scenario

Introduction

Lisa Weierbach is changing to a new school due to her family's move from Brandenburg to Ebersberg in Bavaria. Before classes resume, she uses the BuddyFinder to search for other chemistry enthusiasts in her age group (advanced chemistry course) to discuss the 10th-grade material before school starts and to update her progress during the holidays.

Problem definition

Lisa would like to know where she can find information and materials on the learning level of a 10th-grade student in the subject of chemistry in the state of Bavaria, and how she can prepare for the new school year.

Background and context

Lisa spent most of her school years in Brandenburg, where she had already chosen her advanced courses. Moving to Bavaria confronts her with new challenges, as the curricula and learning levels may be different at the new school. In addition, she will not be able to continue her advanced courses or will have to choose them again. It is important to her to prepare as best as possible for her classes to avoid any gaps and to feel confident in the courses.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Lisa is nervous about changing schools, as she's not sure how to prepare for the classes at her new school. She is worried regarding the uncertainty about the learning level and the possible differences between Brandenburg and Bavaria. She also feels like she doesn't belong yet and is a bit of an outsider because she doesn't know any of her classmates yet, and she therefore has no opportunity to exchange information or support each other.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

To find answers to her questions, Lisa has already tried browsing her new school's website to find information about her new class and subjects. However, the information provided was very general and didn't help her. She also considered contacting her future year group leader by email, but wasn't sure if this was the right way to get helpful information before the holidays.

Activity scenario

Process "Contact with chemistry-loving 10th-graders"

Step 1: Lisa moves to Eberberg, Bavaria. Since she wants to familiarize herself with the material for her advanced chemistry course before classes start during the holidays, she logs into BIRD.

Step 2: Since Lisa has already been enrolled at the nearby [Grafing High School](#), she can already access the school cloud and connect her wallet. She transfers her registration at the new school to her wallet, along with information about the courses she has chosen.

Step 3: She opens the BuddyFinder, which asks her if she wants to share her data. Lisa agrees.

Step 4: Lisa fills out the search query as follows in order to connect with her fellow chemistry enthusiasts and 10th grade students in the state of Bavaria:

- State: Bavaria

- City: Ebersberg (50km radius)
- School: Gymnasium
- Advanced Course: 10th Grade Chemistry
- Group or Individual: Group

Step 5: The BuddyFinder suggests some students who have already formed a group with the goal of exchanging ideas about the content of their advanced chemistry courses.

Step 6: Lisa contacts the advanced course group via contact request and explains that she recently moved from Brandenburg to Bavaria and will now be attending the 10th grade of a high school in Grafing, where she will be taking the advanced chemistry course.

Step 7: She promptly receives a positive response, as the group confirms her contact request and simultaneously sends her an invitation to the shared workspace in BIRD. As it turns out, a future classmate is even among the group members.

Step 8: Lisa opens the workspace and learns about the topics already covered by clicking through the documents.

Step 9: Lisa writes to her classmate via chat and asks if they can meet before school starts so that Lisa can ask her all the questions she has about school and the teachers.